

The Inhibitory Action of Some Double Salts on the Corrosion of 3003 Aluminium Alloy in Local Supply Water

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Gujarat University campus supply water which is of the geochemical type Na-Ca/Mg-HCO₃-Cl was taken for the study of its corrosive tendency towards aluminium 3003 both under stagnant and moving conditions. Inhibitory action of sodium cobaltinitrite, hexaureachromic chloride, potassium trioxalatocobaltate and potassiumtrioxalato ferriate has been investigated in both the conditions. Hexaureachromic chloride is found one of the efficient inhibitor in both the systems; while potassiumtrioxalatoferriate is found less effective inhibitor. It appears the double salts on ionization provide large negatively charged complexes ions which on adsorption over metal surface provide protection.

PORTER and Hadden¹ have studied the corrosion of aluminium alloys in supply water. They concluded that in supply water nodular pitting type of attack takes place and the necessary combinations of water constituents responsible for nodular pitting are calcium, bicarbonate and chloride ions, and copper salts and dissolved oxygen. Metals when immersed completely in water tend to corrode because of their thermodynamic instability²⁻⁴. Chloride and sulphate ions are highly aggressive from corrosion point of view. No attempt has been yet made to study the inhibitive power of double salts towards corrosion of aluminium alloys in supply water.

In the present investigation an attempt has been made to study the corrosion of aluminium alloy 3003 and influence of some double compounds on it in local supply water. Sodium cobalt nitrite, hexa urea chromic chloride, potassium trioxalato ferriate and potassium trioxalato cobaltate were tested as corrosion inhibitors towards 3003 aluminium alloys in supply water.

Experimental

The aluminium alloy (S.W.G. 22, 1/2 hard) used had the following composition: Al 98, Cu 0.15, Mn 1.0, Fe 0.75 and Si 0.6% (maximum). Rectangular specimens of 4 × 8 cm were used. The preparation, testing and cleaning procedures for specimens adopted were those described by Champion⁵. Experiments were carried out with local supply water of Gujarat University campus. The detailed analysis of water used for the experiments is given in Table 1.

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The experimental procedures were adopted as those described in previous publications^{6,7}.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF LOCAL SUPPLY WATER

	Maximum (ppm)	Minimum (ppm)
CO ₃ ⁻²	Nil	Nil
HCO ₃ ⁻	610	580
Cl ⁻	530	510
SO ₄ ⁻²	82	80
Na ⁺	480	470
K ⁺	N.D.	N.D.
Ca ⁺²	48	44
Mg ⁺²	37	35
Cu ⁺²	0.02	—
SiO ₂	Tr	Tr
T.D.S.	1600	1500
pH	7.6	7.5

Dissolved oxygen 5.0 ml/lit.

N.D. = Not determined

Results

(i) Stagnant condition :

Results are given in Table 2.

In the case of sodium cobaltinitrite the corrosion rate decreased with increase in concentration of the compound. Maximum 96% protection was noted. For all the three durations, it is found to be an excellent inhibitor. Specimens remain ash-coloured before and after cleaning.

TABLE 2—INFLUENCE OF SOME DOUBLE SALTS ON THE CORROSION OF 3003 ALUMINIUM IN LOCAL SUPPLY WATER

Size of specimen : 4 × 8 cm (Stagnant condition)
Temperature : 30° ± 2°

Concentration	30 days		60 days		90 days	
	Loss mg	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Inhibition %
0.0	17.0	—	29.0	—	42.0	—
<i>Sodium cobaltinitrite</i>						
2.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	2.7	84	5.4	81	8.0	81
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.5	91	3.5	85	7.5	82
1.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	1.0	94	2.5	91	6.3	85
2.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.8	95	2.0	93	5.4	87
5.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.7	96	1.7	94	4.2	90
<i>Hexaureachromic chloride</i>						
1.7 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.5	91	2.8	90	5.0	88
3.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.0	94	2.5	91	3.7	91
7.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.7	96	2.3	92	3.5	92
1.7 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.5	97	1.7	94	2.5	94
3.5 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.3	98	1.3	96	2.0	95
<i>Potassium trioxalato cobaltiate</i>						
2.5 × 10 ⁻⁵	5.2	70	11.0	62	17.0	60
4.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	4.8	72	10.0	66	15.0	64
8.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	3.5	79	8.3	71	13.0	69
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	3.2	81	5.8	80	10.5	75
4.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	2.5	85	5.2	82	9.3	78
<i>Potassium trioxalato ferriate</i>						
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	7.5	56	16.6	42	23.0	45
4.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	6.5	62	16.2	44	21.0	50
8.0 × 10 ⁻⁵	5.5	68	13.0	55	18.0	57
2.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.5	68	12.0	58	16.0	62
4.0 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.0	71	11.3	60	16.0	62

Hexaureachromic chloride is found more effective inhibitor than that of sodium cobaltinitrite. Its inhibitive power increases with increase in concentration of the compound. Maximum 98% protection was observed. It acts as an efficient inhibitor for all the three durations. Specimens remain bright after cleaning.

Potassium trioxalato cobaltiate is found somewhat less effective than the inhibitory power of hexaureachromic chloride and sodium cobaltinitrite. The rate of retardation of corrosion increases with increase in the concentration of the compound. Maximum 85% protection was observed at its highest concentration. Its inhibitive power remarkably decreased at longer duration.

Potassium trioxalato ferriate afforded maximum 71% protection at its 4.0 × 10⁻⁴ M concentration. It is comparatively less effective than inhibitory action of other compounds. Pits were observed on the specimens for longer duration; on the whole, it is found as a poor corrosion inhibitor.

(2) Moving conditions :

Results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—WEIGHT LOSS DATA ON CORROSION AND INHIBITORY ACTION ON 3003 ALUMINIUM IN LOCAL SUPPLY WATER (MOVING CONDITION)

Size of specimen : 4 × 8 cm Temperature : 30° ± 3°
Rate of water flowing = 2.2 lit/hr. (average)

Duration :	30 days		60 days		90 days	
	Loss mg	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Inhibition %	Loss mg	Inhibition %
Inhibitor						
Blank	77	—	100	—	140	—
Sodium cobaltinitrite	15.0	81	22.5	78	34.0	76
Hexaurea-chromic chloride	4.0	95	7.5	93	14.0	90
Potassium trioxalato cobaltiate	15.7	80	22.5	78	39.0	72
Potassium trioxalato ferriate	31.0	60	43.0	57	66.0	53

In low flow velocity water (2.2 lit/hr. rate flow) sodium cobaltinitrite afforded 81% protection at 30 days duration and then its inhibitive power decreases with increase in time of exposure. Hexaureachromic chloride is found effective corrosion inhibitor in moving condition. It afforded 95% protection at shorter duration. Its protective power gradually decreases at longer duration.

Potassium trioxalato cobaltiate afforded 80% protection while potassium trioxalato ferriate afforded only 60% protection at 30 days duration. The efficiency of both the compounds decreases remarkably at longer duration. In short, potassium trioxalato ferriate is poor corrosion inhibitor for 3003 aluminium alloy in both the conditions.

Discussion

Compared to stagnant condition, even a slight movement increases corrosion tremendously.

Duration in days	Stagnant condition (loss mg)	Moving condition 2.2 lit/hr. rate flow (loss mg)
30	19	77
60	29	100
90	42	140

The inhibitive film formed in the case of sodium cobaltinitrite and hexaureachromic chloride appears to be more uniform and adherent as compared to that of other compounds. Looking to the inhibitory action of these compounds in stagnant condition hexaureachromic chloride is found very effective even at its lowest concentration i.e., $1.7 \times 10^{-5} M$. Potassium trioxalato ferrate is found comparatively poor corrosion inhibitor. In moving condition its inhibitive power is remarkably decreased. Hexaureachromic chloride is efficient inhibitor in moving condition.

The inhibitive power of these double salts, towards 3003 aluminium may be due to general adsorption over the metallic surface. There is a definite relationship between the values of the $\log \theta/1-\theta$ and \log concentration of inhibitor, where θ is the fraction of active sites of the metal surface covered by adsorbed inhibitor, so that $1-\theta$ is the fraction

of the active sites available for reacting with the solution. A graph of $\log \theta/1-\theta$ against $\log c$ was plotted (Fig. 1). The straight line relationship indicates a linear relation between adsorption and \log concentration of inhibitor and supports Langmuir's adsorption isotherm. Hence the inhibition is due to the adsorption of ionized negatively charged complex ions on the metal surface.

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Fig. 1.